

**MODERN PARADIGM OF EDUCATION AS A FUNDAMENTAL CONCEPT OF SCIENCE.
CONCEPTUAL SCHEME AND SUBJECT MATRIX OF THOMAS KUHN**

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Abstract

The main focus of this scientific research is to determine the change of perception of science paradigm by people in today's world, specifically in Kazakhstan. This research project will adopt a mixed-methods approach, combining both qualitative and quantitative research methods and is expected to provide valuable insights into the modern paradigm of education and its relationship with science. It will contribute to the ongoing debate on the role of science in education, and the challenges and opportunities presented by the modern paradigm of education. The study's findings will be of interest to education policymakers, researchers, and practitioners, providing them with a better understanding of the contemporary trends and challenges in science education. Ultimately, the research project aims to inform the development of effective strategies and policies for improving science education in the modern world.

Keywords: science, perception, people, Kazakhstan, innovations, education.

INTRODUCTION

Relevance of the topic.

Education has been a fundamental aspect of human development throughout history. It has been used as a tool for transmitting knowledge, skills, and values from one generation to the next. However, the way we understand education has evolved over time. In recent years, a modern paradigm of education has emerged, which views education as a fundamental concept of science. This paradigm has gained increasing attention from scholars and practitioners in the field of education.

Formulation of the research problem.

The main questions that we wanted to answer during the research process are as follow:

1. How has the modern paradigm of education evolved over time, and what role has science played in this evolution?
2. How has the emphasis on science and technology affected teaching and learning practices in modern education?
3. What are the challenges and opportunities presented by the modern paradigm of education in relation to science, and how can these challenges be addressed?

Methodology.

This research project will adopt a mixed-methods approach, combining both qualitative and quantitative research methods. The study will involve a review of relevant literature on the modern paradigm of education and its relationship with science. We will discuss the results of the on-line and face-to-face survey conducted by us, particularly their significance in the goal of our research.

Aims and objectives of the dissertation.

The main goal of this scientific research project is to explain and explore the recent science model as a system of some main categories such as ideas, conclusions and principles of scientific thinking in scientific theories and development of revolutions. Also, one of

the aims is to discuss the idea of the scientific work "Conceptual scheme and subject matrix" done by Thomas Kuhn as a standby.

Object of the research.

Object of Research topic: The Theory of Evolution by Natural Selection. The main objectives of this research paper are to explore the modern paradigm of education as a fundamental concept of science, its theoretical foundations, and its implication perspectives on current educational practice. Specifically, examining the modern paradigm of education as a fundamental concept of science, analyzing the relationship between education and science, exploring the impact of modern education on science as well as investigating the role of science in the modern education system.

**I THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF
MODERN PARADIGM OF SCIENCE**

1.1 REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

1.1.1 Introduction.

The Theory of Evolution by Natural Selection is one of the most fundamental and influential scientific theories of all time. It provides a framework for understanding the diversity of life on Earth and how it has changed over time. The theory posits that species evolve over time through a process of natural selection, in which individuals with advantageous traits are more likely to survive and reproduce, passing on those traits to their offspring. This process leads to the gradual accumulation of changes in a population over generations, ultimately resulting in the development of new species.

The idea of evolution had been discussed for centuries, but it was not until the mid-19th century that a scientific theory was developed to explain it. Charles Darwin and Alfred Russel Wallace independently developed the theory of evolution by natural selection, which they presented in a joint paper in 1858. Darwin then published his seminal work, "On the Origin of

Species," in 1859, which provided a comprehensive explanation of the theory and the evidence supporting it.

The theory of evolution by natural selection has been extensively studied and tested since its inception, and it has become widely accepted as the best explanation for the diversity of life on Earth. It is supported by evidence from a wide range of scientific fields, including genetics, paleontology, biogeography, and comparative anatomy.

One of the key features of the theory is that it provides a mechanism for the development of complex adaptations in organisms. Natural selection acts on variations in traits within a population, favoring those that provide a survival or reproductive advantage in a particular environment. Over time, these advantageous traits become more common in the population, leading to the development of new adaptations that allow organisms to exploit new ecological niches or cope with changing environmental conditions.

Another important aspect of the theory is that it provides a unifying framework for understanding the relationships between different organisms. By analyzing the similarities and differences between species, scientists can reconstruct the evolutionary history of life on Earth and infer how different groups of organisms are related to each other. This has allowed researchers to create a comprehensive tree of life, which shows how all living organisms are related to each other through a common ancestor.

The theory of evolution by natural selection has also had important practical applications in fields such as medicine and agriculture. By understanding how evolution works, scientists have been able to develop new treatments for diseases and pests that are resistant to existing drugs or pesticides. They have also been able to improve crop yields by selectively breeding plants with desirable traits.

Despite the overwhelming evidence supporting the theory of evolution by natural selection, it remains controversial in some circles. Some religious and political groups reject the theory because they believe it conflicts with their worldviews or undermines their ideologies. Others misunderstand or misrepresent the theory, leading to misconceptions and misinformation about what it actually proposes.

Nevertheless, the theory of evolution by natural selection remains a cornerstone of modern biology and an essential component of scientific literacy. It has provided a framework for understanding the diversity of life on Earth and how it has changed over time, and it continues to be an active area of research and debate among scientists. By studying and refining the theory, researchers can gain new insights into the mechanisms of evolution and the origins of life itself.

1.1.2 Scientific Paradigms and the Development of Scientific Revolutions.

Science is an ever-evolving field, constantly shaped and influenced by new discoveries, technologies, and ideas. The development of scientific paradigms, or overarching systems of thought and methodology, is crucial to understanding how science progresses over time. The concept of scientific revolutions, where a new paradigm emerges and replaces an old

one, is also fundamental to the history of science. This literature review will examine the concept of scientific paradigms and their role in scientific revolutions, as well as explore some examples of paradigm shifts in science.

A scientific paradigm is a broad framework that encompasses the main ideas, principles, and methodologies that guide scientific inquiry within a particular field. It is a set of assumptions and beliefs that shape the way scientists view the world and approach their research. Kuhn (1962) famously defined scientific paradigms as "universally recognized scientific achievements that, for a time, provide model problems and solutions for a community of practitioners."

Scientific paradigms can be thought of as a lens through which scientists view their subject matter. They provide a set of shared concepts and tools that allow scientists to communicate and collaborate effectively, as well as guide their research agendas. However, paradigms are not static; they evolve over time as new discoveries are made and new ideas emerge.

1.1.3 Scientific Revolutions.

Scientific revolutions occur when a new scientific paradigm emerges and replaces an old one. Kuhn (1962) argued that scientific revolutions are not simply a matter of cumulative progress, but rather a shift in the fundamental assumptions and concepts that guide scientific inquiry. He described scientific revolutions as "a series of peaceful interludes punctuated by intellectually violent revolutions."

One of the most famous examples of a scientific revolution is the shift from the geocentric to the heliocentric model of the solar system. For centuries, the prevailing view was that the Earth was the center of the universe and all other celestial bodies orbited around it. However, in the 16th century, Copernicus proposed a heliocentric model, in which the sun was at the center of the solar system and the planets orbited around it. This revolutionized our understanding of the universe and paved the way for further discoveries in astronomy.

Another example of a scientific revolution is the shift from classical mechanics to relativity. For centuries, classical mechanics had been the dominant paradigm for understanding the behavior of objects in motion. However, in the early 20th century, Einstein developed his theory of relativity, which fundamentally changed our understanding of space, time, and gravity.

1.1.4 Conceptual scheme and subject matrix of Thomas Kuhn.

The main idea from Thomas Kuhn's "Science as a paradigm":

1. Author argued that science does not evolve gradually towards truth.

2. Kuhn stated that science has a paradigm which remains constant before going through a paradigm shift when current theories can't explain some phenomenon, and someone proposes a new theory.

3. A scientific revolution occurs when: (i) the new paradigm better explains the observations and offers a model that is closer to the objective, external reality; and (ii) the new paradigm is incommensurate with the old.

According to Kuhn, after a scientific discipline matures, its history consists of long periods of stasis punctuated by occasional revolutions of this sort. Thus, a scientific discipline goes through several distinct types of stages as it develops. Kuhn divided science into some stages that are: i) pre-science, ii) normal science; iii) model shift and its crisis; iv) model revolution and paradigm change.

1. The pre-science stage refers to a period before a scientific consensus was reached where the statements of the research are diverse and out of order. In addition to that, because of the scientists' theoretical debates there is no commonly accepted view on the topic problem.

2. The most common and stable type of science part is normal science as it has a conventional basis for research that sets a precedent. In this stage ideas that resist solutions are seen as anomalies. Although this stage is considered as a draft scheme, it is necessary for it to be uncritical. If all scientists were critical of a theory and spent time trying to falsify it, no detailed work would ever get done.

3. In this stage anomalies become serious, and a crisis develops if the anomalies undermine the basic assumptions of the paradigm and attempts to remove them consistently fail. Ideas that test the theory are being considered as valid. If the anomalies can be resolved, the crisis is over and normal science resumes. If not, there is a scientific revolution which involves a change of paradigm.

4. If a new paradigm occurs, this stage better explains it and offers a model that is closer to the objective or external reality. As there is no natural measure or scale for ranking different paradigms, non-identical paradigms are held to be incommensurable — the new paradigm cannot be proven or disproven by the rules of the old paradigm, and vice versa.

Thomas Kuhn's work had a huge impact on the philosophy of science, changing the definition of terms like "paradigm shift" and "paradigm," as well as expanding the meaning of the word "paradigm" itself from its previous narrower usage. The term "paradigm shift" is frequently used, which has increased scientists' awareness of and openness to paradigm shifts. As a result, Kuhn's analysis of the development of scientific perspectives has had an independent impact on that development. For Kuhn, logical processes supported, but did not ultimately determine, the choice of paradigm. According to Kuhn, it reflected the consensus of the scientific community. He claimed that accepting or rejecting a paradigm is a societal decision as much as logical process.

The scientific revolutions that replace one paradigm with another do not bring us any closer to understanding how things really are. It is impossible to compare successive paradigms. According to Kuhn, a later paradigm may be a more effective tool for resolving conundrums than an earlier one. Nevertheless, the idea that paradigm shifts are objectively true was refuted by Kuhn using the incommensurability hypothesis. Truth depends on the paradigm.

Science does not abruptly alter its worldview. Younger researchers advance a new paradigm. A new

scientific truth, in the words of Thomas Kuhn, "does not triumph by persuading its opponents and making them see the light, but rather because its opponents eventually die, and a new generation grows up that is familiar with it".

Thomas Kuhn demonstrated that modern philosophers could not disregard the social context in which research is conducted as well as the history of science. The society in which science is practiced shapes it.

1.1.5 Paradigm Shifts in Science

There are many examples of paradigm shifts in science, ranging from the discovery of new technologies to the development of new theories. One example is the shift from classical genetics to molecular genetics. For many years, classical genetics was the dominant paradigm for understanding the inheritance of traits. However, in the mid-20th century, the discovery of the structure of DNA and the development of molecular biology revolutionized our understanding of genetics.

Another example is the shift from a mechanistic view of the brain to a more complex, dynamic view. For many years, the prevailing view was that the brain operated like a machine, with different parts responsible for specific functions. However, in recent decades, advances in neuroscience have led to a more nuanced view of the brain, with a greater emphasis on the complex interactions between different parts of the brain and the role of environmental factors in shaping brain development.

CONCLUSION OF THE 1ST CHAPTER

Scientific paradigms are pivotal moments in the history of science when a new paradigm emerges and replaces an old one, fundamentally changing the way we view and understand the world. The development of scientific paradigms is an ongoing process, driven by the quest for knowledge, innovation, and progress.

The emergence of new scientific paradigms often occurs through a process of crisis, where the existing paradigm fails to explain new observations or phenomena. This crisis leads to a search for new explanations, which can lead to the development of a new paradigm. This process is often slow and incremental, with many competing theories and ideas vying for acceptance.

The concept of scientific revolutions was popularized by Thomas Kuhn, who argued that scientific progress is not always linear or continuous, but rather punctuated by revolutionary changes in our understanding of the world. Kuhn's work on scientific revolutions challenged the traditional view of science as a cumulative and rational process, highlighting the role of subjective factors such as social, political, and cultural factors in shaping scientific knowledge.

The development of new paradigms has led to many significant advances in science, such as the Copernican revolution in astronomy, the Darwinian revolution in biology, and the quantum mechanics revolution in physics. These scientific revolutions have not only changed our understanding of the natural world but have also had profound social, economic, and cultural impacts.

One of the most significant social impacts of scientific revolutions has been the rise of scientific authority and the decline of traditional religious and philosophical authority. The development of new scientific paradigms has challenged the traditional views of the world and has led to the development of new worldviews and cultural norms.

In conclusion, scientific revolutions have played a crucial role in the development of science and have led to significant changes in our understanding of the world. The development of new scientific paradigms is an ongoing process that is shaped by many factors, including social, cultural, and political factors. While scientific revolutions can be disruptive and challenging, they ultimately lead to progress and innovation, paving the way for new discoveries and new ways of understanding the world.

II ANALYTICAL SELECTION OF THE MODERN PARADIGM OF SCIENCE PHENOMENON

2.1. METHODOLOGY

2.1.1 Description of the research methodology used in the study.

This methodology outlines the steps taken to examine scientific paradigms and the development of scientific revolutions. The aim of this research is to understand the nature of scientific paradigms, their role in scientific revolutions, and some examples of paradigm shifts in science. The following sections describe the research design, data collection methods, and data analysis techniques used in this study.

2.1.2 Data collection methods and sources.

This study used a qualitative research design, which is well-suited for exploring complex social phenomena such as scientific paradigms and revolutions. The research design was based on a review of relevant literature in the field of science studies, including books, journal articles, and other scholarly publications. The literature review was used to identify key concepts, theories, and examples related to scientific paradigms and revolutions.

2.1.3 Data analysis techniques.

The primary data collection method used in this study was an on-line and face-to-face communicative survey of students from Kazakh-British Technical university and the secondary was a systematic literature review. This involved searching for and analyzing relevant literature on scientific paradigms and revolutions, including books, journal articles, and other scholarly publications. The search terms used in this study included "scientific paradigms," "scientific revolutions,"

"paradigm shifts in science," and "Kuhnian paradigm shifts."

The literature search was conducted using electronic databases such as Google and the survey was conducted in Microsoft Forms. The search was limited to articles published in English between the years 1960 and 2021. A total of 3 articles were included in the final analysis.

2.2 DATA ANALYSIS

2.2.1 Working with the data.

The data collected in this study was analyzed using thematic analysis. This involved identifying and analyzing patterns and themes in the literature related to scientific paradigms and revolutions.

The first step in the data analysis process was to read and familiarize ourselves with the literature. This involved reading the articles in their entirety and taking notes on key concepts, themes, and ideas. Next, we picked some key information and constructed the scheme based on the key concepts and themes that emerged from the literature. The third step was to conduct an interview survey from 15 people and analyze it by taking notes of the speaker's idea. Next, we made an online survey based on our topic and collected the data from it respectfully.

Finally, we analyzed the constructed data to identify patterns and themes related to scientific paradigms and revolutions. We used thematic maps to visualize the data and identify common themes and patterns.

2.2.2 Working with statistics.

The first question that we asked from the volunteers was: "How does the modern paradigm of education incorporate technology into the learning process?". From that question we have detected that the half of the student agreed that the education is affected more by interpretation of some online learning tools such as "Kahoot" and "Quizzlet", also some learning apps made by Microsoft and Google and etc., rather than other categories. Collectively, we think that, because of the recent activities where schools in Kazakhstan are slowly trying to insert interactive and fun quizzes into the education process, which makes students be more active and interested in the subject during the lessons, can be considered as a strong argument in favor of that statement. Another thing is that the least number of students agreed with the variant about integration of VR in education. It can be manipulated from the fact that VR is not highly and maybe totally not used in schools of Kazakhstan.

How does the modern paradigm of education incorporate technology into the learning process?

The next question was asked in order to analyze the opinions of examined volunteers about the student-centered learning system, which means that the educational system is always in favor and around the student's will. From the pie chart, we can see that about 43% of volunteers chose the variant to work collaboratively as the key principle of student-centered learning

system. This fact is highly appreciated by the student not only in Kazakhstan, but around the world. Communication is considered as a "key to everything" in many social circles. And the least voted for variant was about "self-improving". People would not appreciate it if schools established the direction of self-improving, because the "self" is not for everyone.

What are the key principles of student-centered learning in the modern paradigm of education?

Finally, the last question was asked to analyze the opinions of students about the future of science interpretations in education system of Kazakhstan. The results were pretty interesting for us. The majority of students were for the idea to increase the competitiveness at schools by minimizing the diversity of being able to access the resources among the students. This is a big

problem around the world, particularly in Kazakhstan nowadays. The difference in level of quality of education is drastic as urban people have higher access to educational resources than the rural ones because of the centralized system to the main cities of a regions in country. So, the problem should be taken into consideration by the government.

How can the modern paradigm of education be adapted to better serve the needs of diverse student populations?

2.2.3 Conclusion of survey.

From the survey that we conducted we may conclude that problems that we detected in Kazakhstan are equal to the problems around the world. Kazakhstani educational system is slowly evolving by trying new approaches in order to fix and develop the education using modern scientific phenomena. But, overall to increase the science in the whole country, the government of Kazakhstan Republic should pay more attention to the rural regions and develop science interest around people there. Because KR is still not highly savvy in the science field.

CONCLUSION OF THE 2ND CHAPTER

The study of science paradigms is an important area of research that helps to understand the development of scientific theories and the revolutions that have shaped the course of scientific progress. This research aims to explore the research methods and process for studying science paradigms.

The research methodology for studying science paradigms is an interdisciplinary approach that combines different research methods and techniques to collect and analyze data. The following research methods and techniques are commonly used in studying science paradigms:

A literature review is a systematic and critical analysis of existing literature on a specific topic. It helps to identify key categories, ideas, conclusions, and principles of scientific thinking in different science paradigms. The literature review also helps to identify

gaps in the existing literature and areas that require further research. Case studies are in-depth analyses of a particular phenomenon or event. In studying science paradigms, case studies can be used to examine specific revolutions or scientific theories that have shaped the course of scientific progress. Case studies involve collecting data through interviews, observations, and analysis of archival documents. Surveys are a quantitative research method that involves collecting data from a large sample of participants. Surveys can be used to collect data on the attitudes, beliefs, and knowledge of individuals about different science paradigms. Surveys can be conducted online or through telephone or mail.

The data collected through different research methods and techniques can be analyzed using different data analysis techniques. The following data analysis techniques are commonly used in studying science paradigms:

1. Content Analysis: Content analysis is a qualitative research method that involves analyzing textual data to identify patterns, themes, and categories. In studying science paradigms, content analysis can be used to analyze the categories, ideas, and principles of scientific thinking in different scientific theories and revolutions.

2. Statistical Analysis: Statistical analysis is a quantitative research method that involves analyzing numerical data to identify patterns, relationships, and trends. In studying science paradigms, statistical analysis can be used to analyze the data collected through surveys or experiments.

CONCLUSION

The study of science paradigms is an interdisciplinary approach that involves the use of different research methods and techniques. A combination of qualitative and quantitative research methods can be used to collect and analyze data on the categories, ideas, and principles of scientific thinking in different science paradigms. Data analysis techniques such as content analysis and statistical analysis can be used to analyze the data collected through different research methods. The research on science paradigms aims to contribute to a better understanding of the development of scientific theories and revolutions and their impact on scientific progress.

This study used a qualitative research design and systematic literature review to examine scientific paradigms and revolutions. The data were analyzed using thematic analysis, and patterns and themes related to scientific paradigms and revolutions were identified. The findings of this study provide insights into the nature of scientific paradigms, their role in scientific revolutions, and some examples of paradigm shifts in science.

The state of scientific paradigm in Kazakhstan is relatively poor and not well spread across the country. The interest among the youth generation is not active. So, the government should focus on the development of interest in science of future generations in order to be competitive and be time-to-time with the new innovations in that field which can help not only the educational level but can support the country economically.

The dissertation may explore different science paradigms, such as the Copernican revolution, the Darwinian paradigm, or the quantum mechanics paradigm, and analyze their main categories, ideas, conclusions, and principles of scientific thinking. The dissertation may also discuss the development of scientific theories and the role of scientific revolutions in shaping science paradigms. Criticisms and debates surrounding science

paradigms, such as Kuhn's theory of scientific revolutions may also be examined. The dissertation may use both qualitative and quantitative research methods, such as literature reviews, case studies, or surveys, to collect and analyze data. Overall, the dissertation aims to contribute to a better understanding of science paradigms and their impact on scientific thinking and progress.

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